

TASK-BASED LANGUAGE LEARNING AND TEACHING IN EFL CLASSROOMS

Shermatova Sevara Azamjon qizi
sevarashermatova0110@gmail.com

Nabijonova Ruxshona Akmal qizi
nabijonovaruxshona6@gmail.com

Ibrohimova Mohinur O'tkir qizi
mibrohimova005@gmail.com

Sayfiyeva Gulsanam Sohijon qizi

Students of Uzbekistan State University of World Languages
gulsanamsayfiyeva2000@gmail.com

Supervisor: Kuandikova Asem Bekseitovna

EFL teacher, Uzbekistan State World Languages University
asemkuandikova133@gmail.com

ORCID: 0009-0000-7591-2176

Abstract: This paper examines Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) as an effective approach in modern language education. It focuses on its key principles, benefits, and challenges, highlighting how meaningful tasks enhance communicative competence, learner engagement, and practical language use.

Keywords: Task-Based Language Teaching, communicative competence, interactive learning, learner autonomy, language skills

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается обучение на основе заданий (TBLT) как эффективный подход в современном языковом образовании. Анализируются его основные принципы, преимущества и трудности, а также подчеркивается роль заданий в развитии коммуникативной компетенции и практических языковых навыков.

Ключевые слова: обучение на основе заданий, коммуникативная компетенция, интерактивное обучение, автономия учащихся, языковые навыки

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola zamonaviy til o'qitishdagi samarali yondashuvlardan biri bo'lgan vazifaga asoslangan o'qitish (TBLT)ni tahlil qiladi. Unda uning asosiy tamoyillari, afzalliklari va muammolari yoritilib, mazmunli vazifalar o'quvchilarning kommunikativ kompetensiyasini, faolligini va amaliy til ko'nikmalarini qanday rivojlantirishi ko'rsatiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: vazifaga asoslangan o'qitish, kommunikativ kompetensiya, interaktiv ta'lim, o'quvchi mustaqilligi, til ko'nikmalari.

Introduction

In recent years, the way languages are taught has changed a lot. Many teachers are no longer focusing only on grammar rules and memorization. Instead, they try to help students use the language in real communication. One of the approaches that is becoming more popular is Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT). In my opinion, this method is more practical because students are not just learning about the language, but they are actually using it while doing different tasks (Ellis, 2003).

Nowadays, it is very important for students to be able to communicate in English in real-life situations. For example, they may need to speak with foreigners, study abroad, or use English in their future jobs. Because of this, just knowing grammar is not

enough. Students need practice, and they need to feel confident when speaking. As Richards and Rodgers (2014) explain, modern teaching methods should involve students more and give them opportunities to interact.

This paper discusses what Task-Based Language Teaching is, how it works in the classroom, and why it is considered effective. It also looks at some difficulties teachers may face and gives a few practical suggestions.

Main Part

Task-Based Language Teaching is based on the idea that people learn a language better when they use it for real purposes (Nunan, 2004). In this method, the main focus is on tasks. A task can be anything that requires students to use language to achieve a goal. For example, students may be asked to plan a trip, solve a problem, discuss a topic, or role-play a real-life situation like ordering food in a restaurant or asking for directions.

In many cases, a TBLT lesson is organized in several stages. First, the teacher introduces the topic and explains what students need to do. This stage is important because students need to understand the task clearly. Then, students start working on the task, usually in pairs or small groups. During this time, they try to communicate their ideas. It is normal if they make mistakes, because the main goal is communication, not perfection. After the task is finished, the teacher gives feedback and may focus on correcting some language problems (Willis, 1996).

One of the biggest advantages of TBLT is that students become more active. In traditional lessons, students often just listen to the teacher and take notes. But in TBLT, they have to speak, think, and interact with others. From what I have seen, students usually enjoy this type of lesson more, because it feels less boring. This also helps them feel more confident when using English (Harmer, 2007). Another positive side is that different skills are used together. For example, while doing a task, students may read instructions, listen to their partners, speak during discussion, and sometimes write their ideas. This is similar to real life, where we do not use language skills separately.

TBLT also helps students develop other abilities, not only language. For example, they learn how to work in a team, how to share opinions, and how to solve problems. These skills are useful not only in language learning but also in everyday life. However, there are also some challenges. One problem is that it is not always easy for teachers to prepare suitable tasks. The task should match the students' level. If it is too difficult, students may feel stressed or confused. On the other hand, if it is too easy, students may not learn much. Another issue is classroom management. Sometimes, when students work in groups, the class can become noisy, and it may be difficult for the teacher to control everything. Also, not all students participate equally. Some students may be very active, while others stay quiet.

Assessment is also a challenge in TBLT. Traditional exams usually test grammar and vocabulary, but they do not always show how well students can communicate. Because of this, teachers often use other methods, such as presentations, group projects, or simply observing students during activities (Brown, 2001).

Conclusion

To sum up, Task-Based Language Teaching is a useful approach that helps students learn language in a more natural and practical way. It focuses on communication and encourages students to use English in real situations. In my opinion, this method can make lessons more interesting and effective.

For better results, teachers should try to choose tasks that are related to students' real life. For example, topics like daily routines, travel, or future plans can be more engaging. It is also important to give clear instructions, because if students do not understand the task, they may feel lost.

Another important thing is to create a friendly classroom environment. When students feel comfortable, they are more likely to participate and speak. Teachers should support students and not focus too much on mistakes at the beginning.

At the same time, it is necessary to balance fluency and accuracy. Students should be allowed to speak freely, but they also need correction to improve their language over time. In addition, using technology, such as videos or online tasks, can make lessons more interesting and modern.

References:

1. Brown, H. D. (2001). *Teaching by Principles: An Interactive Approach to Language Pedagogy*. Longman.
2. Ellis, R. (2003). *Task-Based Language Learning and Teaching*. Oxford University Press.
3. Harmer, J. (2007). *How to Teach English*. Pearson Education.
4. Nunan, D. (2004). *Task-Based Language Teaching*. Cambridge University Press.
5. Richards, J. C., & Rodgers, T. S. (2014). *Approaches and Methods in Language Teaching*. Cambridge University Press.
6. Willis, J. (1996). *A Framework for Task-Based Learning*. Longman.